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Critical Analysis Of Influence Of Social Media For Enhancing Entrepreneurship Education In Colleges Of Education In South-South, Nigeria

Oweisana, Akpokabowei Ph.D

**Entrepreneurship education Department
Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State, Nigeria
akposino@yahoo.com**

ABSTRACT

The study adopted descriptive survey design. This design was considered appropriate for the study as it collected data on the opinion of Entrepreneurship educators and learners in colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 257 respondents made up of 70 Entrepreneurship educators and 187 students of Entrepreneurship Education. The simple random sampling techniques was used and the data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The instrument was constructed using a five-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) 5 points, High Extent (HE) 4-point, Moderate Extent (ME) 3point, Low Extent (LE) 2points and Very Low Extent (VLE) 1point. The questionnaire was validated and the reliability index of 0.78 was generated using Pearson Correlation co-efficient. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions. It was recommended that the College of Education students should be enlighten and sensitized on the effective use of social media platforms for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship education in schools.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, schools,

INTRODUCTION

The world today is celebrating the improvements in communication technology which has broadened the scope of communication through Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Modern Technologies in communication no doubt have turned the entire world into a “Global village,” (Jonah, 2013). However, as it is, technology like two sides of a coin, bring with it both negative and positive sides. It helps people to be better informed, enlightened, and keeping abreast with world developments. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been regarded as one of the fastest growing sectors in the world in contemporary times (Lagi, and Raja, 2017). The advancement of ICT has given rise to developments and the birthing of rapid changes in the society by shaping the global economy. Significant changes in industries, education, agriculture, medicine, business, engineering and other fields have been brought about by ICT. Within the past decades, new ICT tools such as smartphones and tablets have provided sufficient incentives for enhancing communications and entrepreneurial activities. The emergence of Social networking sites such as: Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp and 2go, have made communication a lot more easier in recent times; According to Atim, Adelabu, Onekutu, Olukunle and Atim (2019), one of the breakthroughs in information and Communication technology in the 21st century was the discovery and emergence of the new media (social media) which have facilitated the creation of

different platforms for social media interaction. These have given rise to multiple networking sites which are used by most people to interact with old and new friends, physical or internet friends.

Entrepreneurial education has recently become the foundation of economic development worldwide. The growing recognition of the role entrepreneurship plays in job creation, innovation, and economic growth has prompted educational institutions to incorporate entrepreneurial programs into their curricula (Fayolle, 2013). Entrepreneurship education, which has recently gained prominence, means many things to different educators. According to Kourilsky (2023), entrepreneurship education consists of identifying opportunities, marshaling resources in the face of danger, and establishing a commercial endeavor. Bechard and Toulouse (2018) define it as a set of codified teachings that informs, trains, and educates everyone interested in small business establishment or development. It also has diverse meanings at various levels of schooling. At the primary and secondary school levels, the goal is primarily to raise awareness of a career path, and so it acts as a vehicle for the development of academic abilities and emphasis on the value of school subjects. As a result, they acquire mastery of several topics, particularly English and Mathematics.

Entrepreneurship education is seen at the postsecondary level of education as a means of improving a person's skills to succeed in both the workforce and as an entrepreneur, in addition to being a career possibility. Thus, it follows that the development of entrepreneurial competence is the main goal of entrepreneurship education. It is the process of giving people the insight, zeal, expertise, courage, and abilities to act on business possibilities that they identify. Thus, the goal of entrepreneurship is to educate people, particularly young people, to be responsible and enterprising people, to think deeply about entrepreneurship, and to subsequently contribute to the sustainable and economic development of their communities. It fosters original thought as well as a strong sense of accountability and self-worth. Graduates with an entrepreneurial mindset, particularly those with postsecondary degrees, are more able to innovate and become self-employed job "creators" rather than just "seekers" of employment.

Despite its increasing importance, several contemporary issues persist within the field of entrepreneurial education. These issues include the mismatch between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, the limited integration of diverse entrepreneurial approaches, and challenges regarding accessibility for underrepresented groups. Addressing these issues is vital for creating a more effective and inclusive entrepreneurial education system. The study investigates the key contemporary issues in entrepreneurial education, highlighting the gaps between traditional educational models and the skills needed by modern entrepreneurs. Additionally, the paper examines the role of educational institutions in bridging these gaps and providing students with the tools necessary to thrive in the entrepreneurial world.

Social media is the social interaction among people in which they create, share or exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks.

The invention of interest, particularly the development of interactive version of the web social media have been utilized in educational system to facilitate teaching/learning process. According to Young (2008), social media is a form of electronic communication, such as web sites for social network through which users create online communication to information, ideas, personal messages and other content such as videos. Young also viewed social media as platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Google, Wikipedia, LinkedIn, YouTube, WhatsApp, Beddit and among others, all of which have the general property of bearing internet based applications web 2.0 that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content. User generated content enable the user to be active and creative, that is their content must be openly published to other users rather creation for one's consumable. Social media is a group of internet based application that allows the creation of exchange of user-generated content. It is an offshoot of modern digital communication, which helps to promoted interaction and the sharing of information on real time basis (Kaplan and Haenlein in Ekwue and Osamor 2015). Kaplan and Haenlein stated that social media depend on mobile and web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-orate, discuss and modify use-generated content. Abdulsalam and Azizah (2014) optioned that social media is a two-way process and thus a social network which can facilitate teaching and learning by allowing for prolong interaction between the provider, adult educator

and the recipient of the education (adult learner) has the effect of reinforcing the information provided the recipient progresses.

Nigeria as a developing country has come to recognize the important of technologies in education. The globalized increase in technology has made it imperative for Nigeria to consider the utilization and promotion of technologies as one of the best practices in education. Any nation that wished to attain a height educationally must therefore enthrone technology at the highest level of priority of its visioning, planning and nation-building process.

Social media is a form of electronic communication that facilitates interaction based on certain interests and characteristics; it is the gathering of people in an online community for the purpose of sharing interest and activities together (Kaplan & Haenleinn in Atim & Atim, 2020).

According to Halonen, (2018), Social media entails the process through which people interact by sharing, creating and exchanging information and ideas through virtual communities and networks. In the present days, it is almost a common practice for people to spend a major of their time making use of social networks(Nami, 2010). This is traceable to the fact that it is easy to use and it facilitates speeds and durability. Social media is fast changing the public discourse in societies and setting trends and agendas in topics that range from the environment, education and politics to technology and the entertainment industries. It is therefore obvious that the modern reality requires one to stay in touch and keep abreast with the latest news and trends of time. Users of social networks, in most cases, have been reported, are a representative of the younger generation, including students.

Several studies have shown that students frequently use social media to access information (Junco, 2015). They follow educational pages, watch science-related videos, and engage in discussions on topics of interest. This exposure to diverse perspectives and information sources can potentially stimulate curiosity and interest in subjects like biology (Bargh & McKenna ,2014). On the other hand, the constant notifications, scrolling, and peer interactions on social media can compete for students' time and focus, potentially diminishing their motivation to engage deeply with biology lessons (Kirschner & Karpinski , 2010). The allure of social media can lead to multitasking during study sessions, which may negatively affect learning outcomes (Rosen et al., 2013). The emergence of social media as a result of advancement in technology and expansion in internet software has raised eye brows among academics on its (social media) impact on studies (Asemah, Okpanachi, 2013). Many researchers have argued as touching whether social media use has or has not any impact or influence on students' academic achievement.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is define as the process of teaching individuals the skills, knowledge and mindset needed to launch and grow a successful business or venture. The term "entrepreneurship" refers to a variety of endeavors, such as the following:

- The capacity to invent and construct something from nothing;
- The capacity to combine a clear vision with the attention and tenacity needed to launch a business.
- The ability to recognize an opportunity when others are unable to.
- The capacity to assemble an effective team that will support your own abilities and endeavors
- The capacity to gather, organize, and manage resources wisely
- The aptitude and willingness for innovation and creativity
- The readiness to take on risks, both financial and Personal
- The capacity to persevere through challenges and even overcome them, potentially even turning them to your advantage.

The Benefits of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Education Institutions

There has never been a more important time to study entrepreneurial education than now, since the world faces massive problems that extend well beyond the global economy (King, 2023). The phenomenon has also been sparked by the recognition of its significance for economic advancement. Nigerian educational institutions offer entrepreneurial education with several noteworthy benefits, including the following:

1. **Improving the Academic Performance of Students:** In addition to teaching students how to manage a business, entrepreneurship education also promotes creative thinking, a strong feeling of responsibility, and self-worth, as was previously indicated. This illustrates how the phenomenon maintains people committed to their careers, particularly young people who, for whatever reason, lack enthusiasm in a formal educational setting. These folks include those who are gifted or talented, as well as those who are financially or physically challenged. Such individuals are motivated and equipped to work toward their objectives through entrepreneurial education, which emphasizes other academic disciplines like self-worth. Students who possess this kind of motivation succeed academically and finish their school. The thesis put forth by Charney and Libecap (2013) was that entrepreneurship is an important educational innovation that promotes learning about learning.
2. **Improving Student Performance and School Quality:** Students' improved performance raises both the general performance of the students and the quality of the school. It is predicated on the notion that students who opt to attend classes rather than skip them or drop out may find success through entrepreneurship. As they acquired the capacity to profit themselves, they also impacted the caliber and ranking of the schools.
3. **Aids in the Realization of Educational Goals:** The inclusive education program is currently the goal of education worldwide. It is impossible to overstate the importance of entrepreneurial education to the implementation of this program. As was previously demonstrated, entrepreneurial education inspires pupils and maintains their interest despite their unique issues and difficulties. They consequently gain from education as a result of their increased interest in academic subjects.
4. **Increasing Economic Competitiveness:** The development of sectors that can generate income and jobs has become a key indicator and pillar of any country's future economic progress, particularly in the wake of the global economic crisis. The only people who can start and maintain such industries are those with exceptional entrepreneurial skills. Therefore, it is impossible to overstate the advantages of entrepreneurship in this field. This is due to research demonstrating that, despite popular belief that entrepreneurs are born, this is not the case. According to Gottlieb and Ross (2017), certain aspects of entrepreneurship may be taught and learned, and entrepreneurs are created, not born. Therefore, expanding training and educational options benefits those who aspire to be entrepreneurs.
5. **New Study Program:** Since entrepreneurship education offers a fresh curriculum for both teaching and research, it is also advantageous to humanity. Additionally, entrepreneurship education provides greater hands-on instruction in the development of skills pertinent to the demands of a changing world. This contrasts with traditional business studies, which, despite being well-attended, only emphasize big corporations over startups or small businesses (Oluwafunmilola, 2024). These factors have led to an increase in young people's demand for entrepreneurship education. Cooper, Bottomley, and Gordon (2014) wrote on this and claimed that students' unprecedented need for a business education that will provide them with transferable skills has fueled the growth of programs in entrepreneurship education. This supports Porter's (2014) earlier conclusion that, whereas traditional business schools tend to overemphasize corporate and quantitative procedures at the expense of more creative talents, entrepreneurial education stresses imagination, innovation, and risk-taking in business.
6. **Poverty Reduction and Economic Growth:** Through entrepreneurship, people can take advantage of chances to create wealth and establish a system of incentives that encourage, denounce, and penalize corruption in addition to rewarding hard effort. People, especially young people, are able to generate prospects for work and, as a result, cash by doing this. Income creation encourages saving and investing, as well as the formation of businesses and industries that serve as important drivers or indicators of economic expansion.

The Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Educational Institutions

Even though entrepreneurship education has many advantages, it is still in its infancy in Nigeria. The following issues prevent entrepreneurial education from developing in Nigerian educational institutions:

1. **Finances:** A significant amount of money is required for practical entrepreneurship education instruction. In Nigeria, financing for entrepreneurship education is lacking. Inadequate attempts are being made by the Nigerian government to advance entrepreneurial education (Charney & Libecap, 2013).
2. **Education and Manpower:** There is a dearth of qualified teachers to teach entrepreneurship. Students are not given the skills necessary for success in business by the curriculum (Oluwafunmilola, 2024).
3. **Inadequate Technology and Equipment:** Most Nigerians, especially recent graduates, cannot afford the expensive equipment. Given how closely technology and entrepreneurship are intertwined, this makes it harder for entrepreneurship to grow. As a result, it highlights the necessity of having accessible technology.
4. **Financial Pressure from Parents:** Some Nigerian parents frequently exert a lot of pressure on their children, favoring short-term financial gain over the long-term advantages of education. This makes it challenging for young people to dedicate the necessary time for entrepreneurship training. Nigeria also has a high percentage of underage laborers who lack entrepreneurial skills as a result of these pressures.
5. **Education:** Skilled labor is essential for entrepreneurship. Our educational system falls short in laying the groundwork required to produce such a workforce. There is currently a lack of a well-developed curriculum in our higher education institutions that prioritizes measures to boost accountability (Charney & Libecap, 2013).
6. **Entrepreneurial Attitude:** Nigeria's abundant natural riches and affluence have significantly contributed to the complacency of the country's people and government. The vast majority of Nigerians have idealistic beliefs and, in certain situations, live in wealth that is more imagined than real. Furthermore, there is little to no concern regarding entrepreneurship education because it is thought that there is a strong climate for entrepreneurs. Poor performance in business is caused by a lack of the necessary drive for an entrepreneur. The claim made by Akpa (2017) that the typical entrepreneur is tough and aggressive lends credence to this viewpoint.
7. **Data:** There has been a dearth of data for entrepreneurial education. The design of programs for entrepreneurial education is either nonexistent or very limited.
8. **Insufficient Infrastructure:** There are more issues preventing the advancement of entrepreneurial education as a result of inadequate infrastructure, which includes things like good roads, energy, information access, water supply, etc. Ideas and goods are tough to communicate with other locations. Entrepreneurship cannot reach its full potential without sales (King, 2023).
9. **Cultural Barriers:** A culture that values taking risks is necessary for entrepreneurship. Value creation from information is impossible without a risk-taking mindset. Given Nigeria's unique cultural heritage, which frequently acts as a barrier to investment, it is imperative that the country's risk-taking culture be appropriately addressed (King, 2023).

Strategies to Promote Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Educational Institutions

To encourage entrepreneurial education in Nigerian higher education institutions, the following strategies can be used (Balogun, 2023):

1. **Include entrepreneurship in the curriculum of the schools:** To foster an entrepreneurial mindset at a young age, include entrepreneurship education into the curricula of elementary, secondary, and university education (King, 2023).
2. **Entrepreneurship clubs and organization:** Establish groups and organizations focused on entrepreneurship in schools and communities to give business owners a place to connect, exchange ideas, and gain knowledge from one another.
3. **Workshops and training programs:** To give students real-world experience and expertise, regularly schedule workshops, seminars, and training programs.
4. **Mentorship program:** Assist young business owners by matching them with seasoned business owners and mentors who may offer advice and assistance.
5. **Program for incubation and acceleration:** Create a program for incubation and acceleration to offer resources, capital, and assistance to new and early-stage enterprises.

6. **Entrepreneurship competitions:** To promote creativity and entrepreneurship among students, set up contests and pitch sessions.
7. **Collaboration with industry experts:** Working together with industry professionals: asks successful businesspeople and industry experts to share their knowledge and offer insights into the road of becoming an entrepreneur.
8. **Access to funding and resources:** Grants, capital, and resources should be made available to entrepreneurs in order to help them launch and expand their enterprises (Suleiman, 2016).
9. **Entrepreneurship education:** Provide educators with entrepreneurship education training to make sure they are prepared to guide and instruct pupils in an efficient manner.
10. **Partnership and cooperation:** to advance entrepreneurship education and assist entrepreneurs, encourage cooperation between educational institutions, governmental bodies, and private groups.

Constructivist Learning Theory

Piaget (1954) emphasize that learners have the ability of constructing their understanding of the world and knowledge through experiences and social interaction with their peers and the environment. That learner's previous knowledge comes to bear in his/her learning process and it sharpens their critical thinking.

Practical Applications of Constructivist Learning Theory in Entrepreneurship Education

1. **Problem-Based Learning (PBL):** Learners are given complex real-world problems to solve. This encourages them to apply their knowledge, think critically and collaborate with others. Facilitators guide learners through the problem-solving problems rather than providing direct instruction.
2. **Discovery Learning:** Learners are encouraged to discover information for themselves through experiments, research projects and exploration. This fosters a deeper understanding and promotes curiosity and independent thinking.
3. **Scaffolding:** Facilitators provide support and evidence to help learners achieve tasks they cannot accomplish alone. As learners become more proficient, the supports is gradually removed. Scaffolding helps bridge the gap between current abilities and potential learning goals.

Statement of the Problem

An increase expectation is placed on the role that social media can play to enhance effective entrepreneurship knowledge. It should be noted that there is still a gap between the ambition for interactive learning through technology and the realities of the educational practice. When it comes to evolution of social media, time moves so fast and so many meaningful advances have occurred in the sphere of educational system. The widespread use of social media among pre-service teachers has sparked concerns about its potential influence on their entrepreneurship interest. As digital natives, today's students are deeply engaged in a digital environment that provides them with extensive access to information, various viewpoints, and social connections. Although, social media offers opportunities for enriched learning and engagements, it also introduces challenges that could potentially diminish students' interest for studying entrepreneurship education.

Instead of many students to be using the advantages of social media, they are allowing it to affect their educational programmes which is causing decline in students' interest in learning entrepreneurship education. Students exhibits poor grammatical skills, achieve low grades, not serious about their education and host of others. Even, instead of them to use social media to advertise their products, they prefer using it for other purposes. This research wants to investigates the influence of social media for enhancing entrepreneurship education in colleges of education in south-south, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of social media for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the extent to which social media is utilized to enhance effective Entrepreneurship Education delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria.

2. Examine the extent to which social media utilized act as best practice in Entrepreneurship Education Programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does social media utilized enhanced effective Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria?
2. To what extent is social media utilized act as best practice in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. A survey research design is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire of the entire group (Trinity, 2023). This design, therefore, was considered appropriate for the study as it collected data on the opinion of Entrepreneurship Education educators and learners in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria.

The population of the study comprised of 257 respondents made up of 70 Entrepreneurship educators and 187 students of Entrepreneurship Education. The simple random sampling technique was used and the data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The instrument was constructed using a five point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) 5 points, High Extent (HE) 4 point, Moderate Extent (ME) 3 point, Low Extent (LE) 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) 1 point. Two experts in Entrepreneurship and measurement and evaluation validated the questionnaire. The questionnaire has a reliability index of 0.78, which was established through Pearson Correlation coefficient. Only 254 copies representing (94%) out of 257 copies of the questionnaire was retrieved and found usable. Data collected were analyzed using means and standard deviation for the research questions.

Very High Extent (VHE)	5 points
High Extent (HE)	4 points
Moderate Extent (ME)	3 points
Low Extent (LE)	2 points
Very Low Extent (VLE)	1 points

RESULT

Research Question One: *To what extent does social media utilized enhance effective Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean rating and standard deviations of responses on the extent to which social media utilized enhance Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in tertiary institutions in South – South, Nigeria (n=254).

S/N	Items	Xl	Xs	Xg	S. D	Decision
1.	e-mail enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.59	4.59	4.69	0.62	VHE
2.	Google enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.63	4.63	4.65	0.47	VHE
3.	WhatsApp enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.13	4.13	4.39	0.73	HE
4.	Facebook enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	3.33	3.33	3.44	0.84	ME
5.	Twitter enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	3.26	3.26	3.44	0.97	ME
6.	3D virtual word enhances Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.16	4.16	4.74	0.68	HE
7.	Blog enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	3.38	3.38	3.42	0.72	ME
8.	Linkedin enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	3.73	3.73	3.85	0.88	HE
9.	Wikis enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.75	4.75	4.73	0.43	VHE
10.	Discussion forum enhance Entrepreneurship Education delivery	4.86	4.86	4.84	0.35	VHE

Note: Xl = mean of lecturers; Xs = means for students; Xg = Grand Mean; VHE = Very High Extent; ME = Moderate Extent.

The data presentation in the table 1 showed that the grand mean ratings of respondents on items 3, 4, 7, 8 and 9 were 4.64, 4.74, 4.60, 4.85 and 4.68 respectively within the boundary limit of 4.50 – 5.00 on 5 point rating scale. This indicates that the five identified social media platforms were to a Very High Extent utilized for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The grand mean values on item 5 and 6 were 3.80 and 4.26 respectively, which fell within the boundary limit of 3.50 – 4.49 indicating that the two social media platforms were to a High Extent utilized for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The grand mean for items 1, 2 and 10 were 3.45, 3.35 and 3.40 respectively. This indicate that the three social media platforms were to a Moderate Extent utilized for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The standard deviation values of the 10 items ranged from 0.35 to 0.97 which indicated that the responses of the respondents are close to the mean and one another.

Research Questions Two: *To what extent is the social media utilized act as best practice in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean Rating of Responses on the Extent to which Social media Utilization Act as Best Practice in Entrepreneurship Education Programme Delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria (n=254)

S/N	Items	Xl	Xs	Xg	S. D	Decision
1.	WhatsApp act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	3.70	3.94	3.82	0.37	HE
2.	Twitter act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	3.37	3.51	3.44	0.87	ME
3.	Google act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	4.84	4.89	4.87	0.33	VHE
4.	Facebook act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	3.30	3.34	3.32	0.94	ME
5.	E-mail act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	4.80	4.85	4.83	0.37	VHE
6.	Blog act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	3.16	3.44	3.31	0.86	ME
7.	Wikis act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	4.84	4.90	4.88	0.32	VHE
8.	Discussion forum act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	4.73	4.76	4.74	0.53	VHE
9.	3D virtual work act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	4.72	4.96	4.86	0.33	VHE
10.	Linkedin act as be practices in Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery	3.28	3.34	3.31	0.77	ME

Note: Xl = mean of lecturers; Xs = means for students; Xg = Grand Mean; VHE = Very High Extent; ME = Moderate Extent.

The data presented in table 2 showed that the grand mean ratings of responses of the respondents on items 3, 4, 7, 8 and 9 were 4.87, 4.88, 4.74 and 4.86 respectively which were within the boundary limit of 4.50 on 5 – point rating scale. This indicated that the 4 identified social media platforms were to a ‘Very High Extent’ considered by respondents as best practiced in Entrepreneurship Education programme instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The grand mean value of item 6 was 3.83 which fell within it boundary limit of 3.50 to 4.49 suggesting that the social media platform was to ‘High Extent’ considered by respondents as best practice in Entrepreneurship Education programme instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The grand mean values on the remaining four items in the table, specifically, item 1, 2, 5 and 10 were 3.32, 3.44, 3.31 and 3.30 respectively. This indicated that the four social media platforms were to a ‘Moderate Extent’ considered

by respondents as best practice in Entrepreneurship Education programme instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The standard deviation value of 10 items ranged from 0.32 to 0.94 which respondents are close the mean and one another data in the table.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The research question one identified google search, e-mail, discussion forum, 3D virtual world, LinkedIn and WhatsApp stressed that they are social media platforms that were to a High Extent utilized for enhancing effective Entrepreneurship Education programme delivery in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. The findings of this study corroborate with the findings of Adeoti; Ayomide and Peters (2023) which observed that social media can facilitate teaching and learning by allowing for a prolong interaction between the provider, which the adult education and the recipient of the entrepreneurship learner have effect of reinforcing the information provided the recipient progresses. It should be noted that 78% of tertiary institution students uses social media to solve assignment among friends, 80% use it to search information, 52.7% use it to ask questions, while 57% use it to receive feedback, 64% use it for content creation and others use it to publish information (Tajudeen, 2023).

Again, Daniel (2022) stressed that students, teachers and literates use social media platform for educational purposes. Social media platform like e-mail, google, facebook, wikis and host of others enhances motivation, confidence, critical thinking, interactions etc. These can promote entrepreneurship skills among the students promote entrepreneurship skills among the students.

Research question two observed that e-mail, 3D virtual world, WhatsApp, google search, wikis as a social media platform that greatly promote entrepreneurship skills among the undergraduate students even in the South – South region. The findings of the study agreed with the finding of Ogundele (2022) which asserted that social media platforms are effective in teaching and learning among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship Education is not exceptional in the use of google, Facebook, WhatsApp etc.

CONCLUSION

Using social media platforms to teaching Entrepreneurship Education in tertiary institutions. Social media platforms can promote social interaction among entrepreneurship students in tertiary institution in South – South, Nigeria. It makes Colleges of Education learners to share experience and work together to promote teaching and learning in schools. The study showed that social media platforms such as wikis, google search, WhatsApp and e-mail are to ‘High Extent’ which means that they are highly utilized in teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria. Hence, social media promotes the teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in South – South, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of the Colleges of Education and government should make adequate provision for ICT facilities for use, to ensure effective use of social media platforms for teaching and learning in schools.
2. The Colleges of Education students should be enlightened and sensitized on the effective use of social media platforms for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
3. Adequate supply of power and reliable network speed for effective use of social media in teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education should be encouraged.
4. Training and retraining of undergraduates on the use of social media should be take into consideration.

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